

Conservation of Momentum from Special Relativity and Link with Quantum Mechanics?

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Special relativity was developed after nonrelativistic Newtonian mechanics and so the concept of momentum, its conservation, impulse and Newton's third law, action-reaction, were already known. Here we suggest considering a scenario in which one only knows the concept of rest mass and derives a Lorentz transformation which gives rise to two new quantities, E and p . We then note that E and p considered separately have degeneracies. Next, we consider a center-of-mass frame for two bodies and ask whether the new concept has anything to do with a collision. If m and v are the same as well as p , then by symmetry one would suggest that $p, -p \rightarrow -p, p$. Thus, conservation of momentum applies here, but it is possible, due to degeneracies, to have $p, -p$ with different m and v . This then begs the question: Is the interaction sensitive to m and v or only to p ? If it is not sensitive to p , then one may wonder why p emerges from special relativity. Thus, we suggest that the idea of conservation of momentum follows from special relativistic considerations.

The reason we focus on this idea is that in previous notes we argued that free particle quantum mechanics follows from degeneracy in the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$, but independently from p being a quantity which represents impulse (no clock needed to measure it) and finally, also independently from the desire to find a probability which inherently enforces conservation of momentum. We therefore would like to argue that the relativistic scenario contains the other two.

Special Relativity, Momentum, Impulse and Conservation of Momentum

Newtonian mechanics was developed centuries before special relativity and so the concept of momentum (mv), impulse conservation of momentum and Newton's third law of action-reaction were already well established. Here, we wish to start with only the picture of a rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at t and ask: What would a person in a moving frame ($-v$ constant) see (if $x=0, t=0$ and $x'=0, t'=0$)? This leads to the emergence of two "new" concepts E and p .

In particular, m_0 at $x=0, t=0$ must be seen to move with v in the moving frame so:

$$x'/t' = v. \quad ((1))$$

This leads to the 2x2 Lorentz matrix:
$$\begin{vmatrix} g(v) & vg(v) \\ |vg(v) & g(v) | \end{vmatrix} \quad ((2))$$

If one applies this to $(0, m_0)$ as well, then one obtains two new quantities:

$$E = g(v) m_0 \quad \text{and} \quad p \text{ (x direction)} = v g(v) m_0 \quad (\text{We set } c=1 \text{ for simplicity.}) \quad ((3))$$

If one wishes to have the modulus of the vector remain invariant, then one requires a minus sign in the metric so:

$$E^2 - p^2 = m^2 c^4 \quad ((4))$$

This leads to $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ and $E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ and $p(\text{xdirection}) = m_0 v / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \quad ((5))$

m_0 (rest mass) represents a physical state of an object (which may be experimentally verified through inertia or gravity). Thus, E and p should also represent physical states of the object. One is a scalar and the other a vector. At this point, however, it is not at all clear as to the physical significance of p . There is no link with the idea of impulse as of yet or any notion of the conservation of p .

Two Body Collision

We next consider a two body collision in a center-of-mass frame, i.e. one in which the total momentum is 0 (1). In such a case, one has $p, -p$ before. If one has the special case in which m and v as well as p are the same for each particle, then, by symmetry, one would argue that one has $-p, p$ after. In other words, in this special case, one has conservation of p momentum. ((5)), however, shows that if one decouples E and p , then there are degenerate sets of m_0, v which yield the same p . Thus, one need not have m_0 and v be the same in the center-of-mass frame. This then begs the question: Does the force sense the m_0 and v or only p ? Is the case of conservation of momentum a special circumstance which only holds for m_0, v being the same? We argue that given it is p which emerges from special relativity, that it is this quantity which describes the state of a moving object (where motion is the key focus). In such a case, this would suggest that different degenerate p produce the same impulse hit. (This idea may be verified experimentally.) In such a case, the force sees p and $-p$ and by symmetry should create $-p$ and p in all cases in the center-of-mass frame. Thus, the idea of conservation of momentum and p represent the same impulse regardless of m_0, v emerge and are directly connected.

Quantum Free Particle

We have argued in previous notes that the quantum free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ may emerge in several different ways.

In the first case, we noted that: Lorentz invariant $-Et+px \quad ((6))$ has degenerate solutions which define a resolution in t and x , namely:

$$\Delta x \text{ resolution} = \hbar/p \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta t \text{ resolution} = \hbar/E \quad ((7)) \quad \text{such that:}$$

$$\Delta x + n \hbar/p \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta t + n \hbar/E, \quad \text{where } n \text{ is an integer, leave } ((6)) \text{ invariant.}$$

This resolution may be mapped into a function which describes the periodicity, but treats all points within a set of gradation markings the same. We have argued before that this function

is: $\exp(ipx)$. Furthermore, if one notes that p represents impulse and so does not need a clock to measure it, but also must be associated with motion, then we argued that a particle must carry its own gradation of time and space inherently. This also leads to ((7)).

Finally, we have argued previously that one seeks a probability function which enforces conservation of momentum, then $\exp(ipx)$ suffices because to lowest order in px :

$$\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x) = \exp(i(p_1+p_2)x) \quad ((8))$$

$$\int dx \exp(-i(p_1+p_2)x) \exp(i(p_3+p_4)x) = 0 \text{ if } p_1+p_2 \neq p_3+p_4 \quad ((9))$$

Link with Special Relativity

In the above section, we have suggested that there are at least three seemingly independent approaches to obtaining $\exp(ipx)$. Here, we wish to argue that the special relativistic approach is consistent with the other two. We have argued above that p representing the same impulse regardless of m_0, v and conservation of momentum follow from special relativity. Thus, all three approaches “sit” in special relativity and consistently yield $\exp(ipx)$. The fact that the Lorentz invariant approach leads to an x resolution linked with p , i.e. \hbar/p suggests that features of p , like it representing impulse regardless of m_0, v and its conservation should also be considered. In this case, all of these considerations lead to the same free particle probability (wavefunction) $\exp(ipx)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we first note that the concept of E and p emerge from special relativity, with p being degenerate if decoupled from E . We then ask whether the concept of impulse and conservation of momentum also follow from special relativity in addition to action-reaction and argue that they do.

In previous notes, we suggested that one may obtain the free particle quantum probability (wavefunction) $\exp(ipx)$ using three independent approaches. The first is based on the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$, the second on the degeneracy of p and the third on conservation of momentum.

Here, we argue that all three of these ideas emerge from special relativity and all lead consistently to $\exp(ipx)$. Thus, we argue that all three are related.

References

1. Nuclear and Particle Physics-Lecture 2 Imperial College of London
<http://www.hep.ph.ic.ac.uk/~dauncey/will/lecture02.pdf>